

West End,
Wootton,
Woodstock,
Oxon.
18/11/1972

Dear Beatrice,

I was very glad to see you at last on Friday. I hope this letter brings up all the points outstanding.

I have filled out your form. As you will see, the passport itself was issued in Teheran. If you foresee any problems over that it will be replaced. I have attached to your form a list of publications. There is a mark against the only strictly Arab publication, my Seminar for Arabian Studies lecture. I enclose a paragraph on pearling. I hope it gives the right impression.

In the strictest confidence, Karen's 1971 budget included allowances of 1,300 Bahrain Dinars which was divided among the staff of five for a period of about four months (The period in the field was, I believe, about three months, but time for preparation, etc. in Denmark was included).

I shall keep you informed of the status of my Oman trip since that is clearly a relevant qualification. I'll send you a draft outline of the relevant history of Qatar this summer.

Yours,